

POLICY BRIEF | MAY 22TH, 2026

Research Ethics Governance for an Engaged University: A Call for Institutional Experimentation at Erasmus University Rotterdam

Key Messages

- > European and Dutch research integrity frameworks are evolving to reflect growing expectations for engagement and societal impact in academic research.
- > Through its strategy 2030, Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR) voices the ambition to become a fully “engaged university.” This ambition demands expanding collaboration with societal partners, thereby increasing the complexity of the university’s ethics governance.
- > Procedural ethics safeguards are no longer sufficient with this strategic goal and the changing research and integrity landscape. Ethics governance must support ongoing ethical judgement and cultivate a shared ethical culture across academia and societal partners.
- > This brief calls on EUR and its faculties to invest in and launch a focused portfolio of institutional experiments testing new support pathways: including proportionate review, community data ethics protocols, cross-faculty learning as well as ethics coaching and embedded facilitation.

Problem Statement

EUR’s ethics governance remains largely organised around one-off, ex ante, procedural review. This model is increasingly misaligned with the university’s strategic ambitions to foster engaged research, open science and open innovation practices. On the one hand, these practices demand ongoing ethical judgements at the researcher level¹, including questions of evolving power dynamics, responsibility for societal impacts, benefit sharing. On the other hand, these practices demand distributed agency and accountability as part of a shared ethics culture. Without reform, institutional risks compound, such as compliance fatigue among researchers, inconsistent interpretations across faculties, and blind spots for relational or long-term harms to societal actors.

Realigning ethics governance with EUR’s renewed commitment to engagement and impact requires governance approaches that move beyond procedural compliance. Research Ethics Review Committees (RERC) and Institutional Review Boards (IRB) play an important role in building a shared ethical culture. To this end, they need institutional space to explore, test, and iterate new forms of ethics review, researcher support, and cross-faculty and cross-sector collaboration.

Why now? A Changing Landscape

Ongoing changes in the science landscape reflect the trend towards increased collaboration of academics across disciplines, and with other actors across sectors and societal contexts.

- > Research career & evaluation: Since 2019, major Dutch science policy bodies (UNL, NFU, KNAW, NWO, ZonMw) have been developing and implementing new academic career pathways, including one focused on societal impact.
- > Research funding: The Dutch Research Council (NWO) is expanding funding schemes for inter- and transdisciplinary research via instruments such as the NWA (National Science Agenda), or the KIN (Dutch Climate Research Initiative).
- > Research infrastructure: Open Science NL sets up initiatives such as national Citizen Science Hubs, or community-led citizen science funding, while the National Expertise Centre for Transdisciplinary Work (NECTR) was founded in 2025.
- > Research and Integrity Codes: The 2023 revision of the European Code of Conduct emphasises “active responsibility” (p. 16) from all actors involved, while the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity is currently under revision in response to these shifts. The National Ethics Council for Social and Behavioural Sciences in the Netherlands (NETHICS) has updated its ethics guidance to include knowledge co-creation and participatory methods, and has dedicated its 2026 annual symposium to ethical dilemmas in participatory research and co-design.

What about data governance?

Existing EU and NETHICS research integrity guidelines already apply to participatory research, and the new Dutch guidelines are expected to do so as well. However, they say almost nothing about participatory data governance. Their data guidance focuses mainly on data protection and privacy (in NETHICS) and on institutional duties for preservation and access (in the EU guidelines).

At the same time, Dutch research data infrastructure has become advanced and robust. This maturity now makes it possible to experiment with new technical and procedural approaches that support participatory data governance, such as the CARE Principles and CARE-informed data practices.

«[A] guideline for ethical review of research involving human participants must take [...] into account [...] the range of research methods applied [, ...] including newer methods such as co-creation.» (‘Code of Ethics’ by NETHICS, 2025, p. 5)

Research Ethics Governance at EUR:

- > Faculties started establishing Research Ethics Review Committee (RERC), with ESSB doing so in 2010 and others following from 2015 onwards. In some faculty and institution contexts, the term Institutional Review Boards (IRB) is used interchangeable with RERC.
- > Today, 11 faculty-based RERC with 64 members across EUR.
- > University-wide ethics review policy implemented in 2021. Ethics review organised at faculty level, with central coordination support.
- > Engagement and Research Services (ERS) organises bi-annual meetings of RERC Chairs to support cross-faculty learning.
- > A 2025 policy review identified three recurrent tensions in EUR's ethics governance: (1) safeguarding versus institutional support, (2) procedural snapshot versus in-situ reflection, and (3) centralised ethical authority versus distributed responsibility. It also identified opportunities for governance reform.

Evidence Base:

Between 2023 to 2025, an action learning study was conducted at EURⁱⁱ. The study combined an internal policy evaluation and an organisational study, in total involving 37 interviewees and around 40 participants from across EUR's RERC in two cross-faculty workshops of around 40 participants from across EUR's RERC. Gaps between institutional procedures and the realities of engaged research were identified. The co-inquiry process informed the development of four future-oriented scenarios for ethics governance at EUR and beyond. (see below)

Highlights of the research process

«It's about building a community of practice where [researchers can] learn from each other and from making mistakes»

«It's not about stopping research but steering it in the right direction.»

What the Co-Inquiry Process at EUR Surfaced:

- > The tensions RERC now face reflect a fundamental reorientation of sciencesociety relations and therefore have no simple answer.
- > This reorientation requires rethinking the purpose and structure of ethics governance itself.

The co-inquiry process opens up four imaginaries for EUR's ethics governance

- > **(1) Purpose:** Should ethics governance primarily safeguard institutional accountability, or also support distributed ethical stewardship across the research lifecycle?
- > **(2) Structure:** Should ethical responsibility sit mainly with centralised RERC, or be distributed across researchers, support roles, societal partners, and communities?

Concretely, we are calling upon EUR and its faculties **to invest in and launch a portfolio of institutional experiments** testing new pathways for ethics governance. Institutional experimentation is needed for each of the imaginaries (see figure above) and carries distinct trade-offs between accountability, flexibility, and legitimacy (see Annex). The pathways below outline a focused portfolio of institutional experiments through which EUR can begin to test what works, for whom, and under what conditions.

Our recommendations and a call for experimentation

Our key strategic recommendations for EUR’s ethics governance on their way to become an ‘Engaged University’ are the following:

- > Reconsider the role and purpose of current research ethics governance to take account of changes in the research policy landscape, of EUR’s strategy and of the research-based imaginaries for ethics governance.
- > Invest in institutional experimentation to develop more appropriate ways of safeguarding accountability and supporting researchers individually and the university at large to engage in good research and build good science–society relations.
- > This experimentation is one way to cultivate a shared culture of ethical learning to strengthen individual and collective judgement across the research lifecycle.

Focused Portfolio	Opportunity at EUR	Viable short term pilot
Proportionate and staged review pathway	ERS is already working closely with research teams conducting engaged, participatory, and impact-oriented research. These collaborations create a practical setting to test review pathways.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Select one faculty or research programme to test clearer exemption criteria and tiered review routes for low-, medium-, and high-risk research > Pilot an “approval-in-principle” route with one research project.
Community and data ethics protocols pathway	EUR has in-house expertise in research data stewardship, and CARE-informed data governance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Work with one or two engaged research projects to pilot the implementation of the CARE Principles or CARE-informed data practices ⁱⁱⁱ.
Cross-faculty learning pathway	EUR already has the infrastructure: the dilemma app, central ethics coordination, biannual RER chairs’ meetings and an Engagement Board.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Use the next chairs’ meeting to compare and learn from two anonymised grey-zone cases > Build a shared case repositories of ethical dilemmas related to societal engagement > Co-design trainings and review pathway criteria with RERCs to ensure coherent support for engaged research
Ethics coaching and embedded facilitation pathway	EUR already has adjacent support roles, including Engagement Officers and engagement- or impact-focused recognition and reward profiles. These roles create a basis for testing embedded ethics support.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Pilot ethics coaching with a group of engaged PhD researchers or research team. > Build on existing groups for an EUR community of practice > Establish confidential hotlines or opportunities for sharing failures

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Additional Information & Resources

Illustrative Scenario	Potential Benefits	Trade-offs	Inspirational Practices
Regulatory Ethics Governance	Strengthens scientific credibility and participant protection; shields researchers and institutions through consistent safeguards	Growing concerns over academic freedom, surveillance, compliance-driven disengagement, and institutional overreach	Risk-based impact assessment in data protection and high-risk AI regulation
Embedded Ethics Facilitation	Positions RERC as guides; supports continuous ethical reflection across the research lifecycle	Requires high investment and slows research pace, which can intensify tensions between procedural integrity and real-world responsiveness	Risk-based impact assessment in data protection and high-risk AI regulation Tallinn and Griffith Universities
Community-Integrated Ethics Stewardship	Enhances legitimacy, benefit sharing, and reciprocity; builds shared responsibility between institutions and societal partners, builds community capacity and enhances impact	Labour burden on communities, exclusion concerns, and weak institutional enforcement, requires integration with research data ecosystem	Indigenous ethics review responsibilities are linked to an Indigenous Education Council at Trent University, guidance on CARE-informed data governance for NL available.
Post-RERC Ethics Ecosystem	Embeds ethics as ongoing practice; enables adaptive, context-sensitive governance	Accountability challenges without formal oversight, uneven practices across context, reflection fatigue among	Clear exemption criteria for low-risk or routine research, such as the 'quality improvement studies' in Canada

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